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Power imbalances within academia: race/belonging/class/activism/advisors/positionality

A Professor and a PhD researcher (both white, male and middle class) approach their colleague who is a Black, queer, female and first generation PhD researcher in their team to write a research grant that focuses on race in academia.

The grant states that collaboration with groups from without academia is encouraged. So, to have a better chance of winning this grant the Black team member gets asked the question to approach a local group of Black activists in their city that have been at the forefront of addressing local and national racist structures the group. While hesitant she asks the group, and the group accepts the offer.

The project (a 3 day conference and 6 months research period) is a success. Mainly because of the innovative perspectives from the activists. However, the Black PhD researcher finds out that the activists have not been paid for their research activities and that their names have been left out of the paper that was submitted to a Journal as a result of the project.

She does not feel safe to take up the topic with the Professor, who also is her advisor. Instead she discusses the topic with the PhD. student advisor (a white working class woman who is a first generation in higher education). The two connect over the topic and decide to discuss the issue with the advisor.

The conversation is hard, but honest. However, after the talk the relationship between the Professor and PhD. candidate deteriorates.